

RESEARCH ARTICLE

PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF ANGANWADI AND BALVATIKA CHILDREN

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17811655>

Abstract:

The childhood period plays a very important role in a person's development. And the school in which they spend their early years of study also plays an important role in this. Therefore, here, the impact of balvatika and Anganwadi on the physical development of a child in the holistic development of childhood has been studied. This research was an ex-post-facto type of research. A purposive sampling method was used to select a total of 1200 children of balvatika and anganwadi. Collection of data was carried out with the help of holistic development. For analysis of data 't' test was used. Looking at the results, it looks that the difference between the physical development of Balwatika boys and Anganwadi boys was found to be significant ($F = 2.19$). Furthermore, no significant difference in physical development was observed between girls from Balvatika and girls from Anganwadi. The effect of area is seen as the difference between urban children in Balwatika and urban children in Anganwadi was found to be significant ($F = 2.84$). Similarly, the effect of rural area is evident as the difference between Balwatika rural children and Anganwadi rural children was found to be significant ($F = 6.37$).

Keywords: Balvatika, Anganwadi, Children, Gender, Area.

Introduction:

According to the Indian concept, the definition of child development is unique. Generally, the development of a child begins after birth. But according to Indian philosophy, there are three stages of child development. Including prenatal development, development during pregnancy, and postnatal development. Thus, Indian philosophy is completely different from the idea that a child develops only after birth. This means that the overall development of a child does not happen only after birth. That is, the child develops before birth and during pregnancy as well. In this regard, many studies have been conducted by the Children's Research University, which also proves that the development of a child also occurs during pregnancy.

While prenatal development has played a significant role in the overall development of a child, the postnatal years in particular also play a significant role. In which "the period from birth to eight

years is very important. During these years, the foundation for the child's all-round development to flourish fully is laid. Along with his physical development, mental, intellectual, emotional, social, linguistic, creative... all aspects of his abilities and skills are developed. During the early childhood period, among the significant changes in all areas of development such as physical, social, emotional and intellectual, cognitive development takes place extensively. He has an increasing vocabulary and more sophisticated language skills (Hurlock, 973)". Any child at any stage of development can be taught any subject intellectually effectively, so a carefully planned, well-organized early education program helps children to provide the necessary experiences for their cognitive development.

Thus, early childhood is one of the most critical periods in human life-long development. During which the foundation of intellectual, cognitive, socio-emotional, language and physical competence is laid. In which Anganwadi and Balwatika play an important role because before the child gets primary education, he goes to centers like Anganwadi or Balwatika for pre-primary education. Not only does most of the brain development take place during these early years, but the foundation of strong physical, social and mental health is also laid during this period. Thus, the exposure of a child to positive, nurturing and culture-specific stimuli in the early years has a strong and direct impact on his future life achievements. In which the role of Anganwadi or Balwatika remains very important. The researcher always wondered at what level of overall development the children of Anganwadi or Balwatika would be. Therefore, the present research was conducted with the aim of giving a result to this thought process.

The purpose of the study by Vyas and Karnam (1986) is to "study the attitude of pre-primary teachers towards Anganwadi, Laboratory and Nursery School. To study the difference in sports facilities available in Anganwadi, Laboratory School and Nursery School. The findings of the present research were as follows. Most of the pre-primary teachers said that sports are of great importance in the school system." The purpose of the study by Mistry and Kaul (1986) is to study "the difference in the development of children at the highest level and the lowest level of Anganwadi centers. The findings of the present research show that there is no significant difference in the development of children at both the levels of Anganwadi and no significant difference in the ability of children." The aim of Shukla's (1990) study was "to examine the impact of family, school environment, and economic and social status on the social development of children aged 5-6 years.

The findings of the present research show that family structure has no effect on the ability of children to react socially. Family size also has no effect on the social development of a child." The main objective of this study conducted by Raizada, Sehgal and Soni (2010) was to evaluate the impact of pre-school education under the ICDS (Integrated Child Development Services) program implemented in Ludhiana district of Punjab on the mental and cognitive development of rural and urban 3- to 6-year-old children. It was found that pre-school education provided by ICDS has a clearly positive and significant impact on the mental and cognitive development of children and that the cognitive ability of children improves with increasing age. The aim of the cross-sectional study conducted by Pratik and Dimple (2022) was "to assess the learning and overall development of 4–5-year-old children attending urban Anganwadi centers. The findings suggest that the inadequate pre-school education facilities in

Anganwadi centers are impacting the learning and development of children and there is an urgent need for integrated nutrition and education efforts.”

Therefore, here the physical and mental development of Anganwadi and Balvatika children has been studied in the context of gender and area.

Objective of the Study:

The objectives of study were as under

1. To measure the physical development of children with respect to Balvatika male and Anganwadi male children's.
2. To measure the physical development of children with respect to Balvatika female and Anganwadi female children's.
3. To measure the physical development of children with respect to Balvatika urban and Anganwadi urban children's.
4. To measure the physical development of children with respect to Balvatika rural and Anganwadi rural children's.

Hypothesis of This Study:

1. There will be no significant difference between the average percentage scores of boys in terms of physical development among Anganwadi and Balvatika children.
2. There will be no significant difference between the average percentage scores of girls in terms of physical development among Anganwadi and Balvatika children.
3. There will be no significant difference between the average percentage scores obtained in terms of physical development of children from Anganwadi and Balvatika compared to the average percentage scores obtained by children from urban areas.
4. There will be no significant difference between the average percentage scores obtained in terms of physical development of children from Anganwadi and Balvatika compared to the average percentage scores obtained by children from rural areas.

Variables of the Study

Balvatika and Anganwadi, gender and area are included as independent variables, while physical development is included as a dependent variable.

Sample:

A total of 700 to 800 children were selected through the purposive sampling method as a sample in the present study. The sample was selected from the Gandhinagar city and its surrounding area.

Personal Information Sheet:

In the present research, the personal information sheet was created by the researcher. Name, Age, type of school, type of parents' education, type of family, gender, area, etc. was included in these sheets.

Holistic Development:

The holistic development criteria developed by researcher. This tool contains 60 items. The reliability and validity of this instrument were found to be high.

Result and Discussion:

Ho1 There will be no significant difference between the average percentage scores of boys in terms of physical development among Anganwadi and Balvatika children.

Table 1: Mean scores of regarding boys with respect to Anganwadi and Balvatika on physical development

Sr No.	Particular	N	M	SD	t	Sig.
1	Balvatika Boy's	376	89.77	14.32	2.19	0.05
2	Anganwadi Boy's	447	87.59	14.11		

Figure 1: Mean Scores on physical development in relation to Anganwadi and Balvatika boys

It is observed that the mean scores in table 1 and figure 1 show that Balvatika boys acquired a higher score ($M = 89.77$) on physical development than Anganwadi boy's ($M = 87.59$). To test the hypothesis, a t test has been calculated. The value of the t ratio between the mean score of physical development of boy's Balvatika and Anganwadi is 2.19, which is significant at the 0.05 level of significance. It means that the hypothesis has not been accepted. From the mean score, it has been seen that the physical development of the Balvatika boy's is significantly higher than that of the Anganwadi boys.

Ho2 There will be no significant difference between the average percentage scores of girls in terms of physical development among Anganwadi and Balvatika children.

Table 2: Mean scores of regarding girls with respect to Anganwadi and Balvatika on physical development

Sr No.	Particular	N	M	SD	t	Sig.
1	Balvatika girl's	434	89.09	14.10	1.01	NS
2	Anganwadi girl's	343	87.98	15.91		

Figure 2: Mean Scores on physical development in relation to Anganwadi and Balvatika girls

It is observed that the mean scores in table 2 and figure 2 show that Balvatika girls acquired a slightly higher score (M = 89.09) on physical development than Anganwadi girls (M = 87.98). To test the hypothesis, a t test has been calculated. The value of the t ratio between the mean score of physical development of girls Balvatika and Anganwadi is 1.01, which is not significant.

H03 There will be no significant difference between the average percentage scores obtained in terms of physical development of children from Anganwadi and Balvatika compared to the average percentage scores obtained by children from urban areas.

Table 3: Mean scores of regarding urban area children with respect to Anganwadi and Balvatika on physical development

Sr No.	Particular	N	M	SD	t	Sig.
1	Balvatika (Urban Area children)	350	88.90	15.02	2.84	0.01
2	Anganwadi (Urban Area children)	438	91.67	11.58		

Figure 3: Mean Scores on physical development in relation to Anganwadi and Balvatika urban area children

It is observed that the mean scores in table 3 and figure 3 show that Balvatika (Urban Area Children) acquired a lower score ($M = 88.90$) on physical development than Anganwadi (Urban Area Children) ($M = 91.67$). To test the hypothesis, a t test has been calculated. The value of the t ratio between the mean score of physical development of Balvatika Urban Area Children and Anganwadi Urban Area Children is 2.84, which is significant at the 0.01 level of significance. It means that the hypothesis has not been accepted. From the mean score, it has been seen that the physical development of the Anganwadi Urban Area Children is significantly higher than that of the Balvatika Urban Area Children.

Ho4 *There will be no significant difference between the average percentage scores obtained in terms of physical development of children from Anganwadi and Balvatika compared to the average percentage scores obtained by children from rural areas.*

Table 4: Mean scores of regarding rural area children with respect to Anganwadi and Balvatika on physical development

Sr No.	Particular	N	M	SD	t	Sig.
1	Balvatika (Rural Area children)	460	89.79	12.58	6.37	0.01
2	Anganwadi (Rural Area children)	352	82.90	17.04		

Figure 4: Mean Scores on physical development in relation to Anganwadi and Balvatika rural area children

It is observed that the mean scores in table 4 and figure 4 show that Balvatika (Rural Area Children) acquired a higher score ($M = 88.79$) on physical development than Anganwadi (rural Area Children) ($M = 82.90$). To test the hypothesis, a t test has been calculated. The value of the t ratio between the mean score of physical development of Balvatika rural Area Children and Anganwadi rural Area Children is 6.37, which is significant at the 0.01 level of significance. It means that the hypothesis has not been accepted. From the mean score, it has been seen that the physical development of the Balvatika rural Area Children is significantly higher than that of the Anganwadi rural Area Children.

Conclusion:

The difference between the physical development of balvatika boy's and Anganwadi boys was found to be significant ($F = 2.19$). Therefore, the pre-formed hypothesis (There will be no significant difference between the average percentage scores of boys in terms of physical development among Anganwadi and Balwatika children) is not accepted. The result shows that the balvatika boys had a higher level of physical development ($M = 89.77$) than the Anganwadi boys ($M = 87.59$). This result proves that there is a positive impact on the physical development of balvatika boys compared to Anganwadi boys. No significant difference was observed in physical development between girls from Balwatika and girls from Anganwadi. In this research, it was concluded that balvatika girls and Anganwadi girls have no impact on physical development. Therefore, pre-formed (There will be no significant difference between the average percentage scores of girls in terms of physical development among Anganwadi and Balwatika children.) is not rejected. The difference between balvatika urban children and Anganwadi urban children was found to be significant ($F = 2.84$). Therefore, the pre-formed hypothesis (There will be no significant difference between the average percentage scores obtained in terms of physical development of children from Anganwadi and Balwatika compared to the average percentage scores obtained by children from urban areas) is not accepted. The result shows that the Anganwadi urban children had a higher level of physical development ($M = 91.67$) than the balvatika urban children ($M = 88.90$). This result proves that there is a positive impact on the physical development of Anganwadi urban children compared to balvatika urban children. The difference between balvatika rural children and Anganwadi rural children was found to be significant ($F = 6.37$). Therefore, the pre-formed hypothesis (There will be no significant difference between the average percentage scores obtained in terms of physical development of children from Anganwadi and Balwatika compared to the average percentage scores obtained by children from rural areas) is not accepted. The result shows that the balvatika rural children had a higher level of physical development ($M = 89.79$) than the Anganwadi rural children ($M = 82.90$). This result proves that there is a positive impact on the physical development of balvatika rural children compared to Anganwadi rural children.

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